

The Prevalence of Blood Transfusion Episodes among Thalassemia Patients at Sporting Hospital Alexandria

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Abstract

Thalassemia is the most prevalent type of inherited anaemia globally. The most prevailing type of chronic haemolytic anaemia in Egypt is beta thalassemia, around 85.1%. Treatment of thalassemia includes blood transfusions, iron chelating agents, folic acid (Vit B9) and splenectomy. Regular transfusion protocol should only be initiated if the patient suffers from one of the following: hemoglobin level of ≥ 7 g/dl couldn't be reached or growth impairment or progressive enlargement in spleen size. Splenectomy is needed when blood transfusions surpass 200–250 ml/kg/year of PRBC. Patients on regular PRBC transfusions are vulnerable to the following risks: haemolytic reactions, transmission of infection and iron over load. The aims of the current study was the assessment of the prevalence of blood transfusion episodes among thalassemia patients and evaluation of the relationship between the blood transfusion (regarding frequency and type of transfusion) and sociodemographic factors, clinical and laboratory findings. A cross sectional study was conducted. The data was collected from the medical records of 73 thalassemia children patients at Sporting Hospital, Alexandria. The current study showed that splenectomy had a significant effect on the frequency of blood transfusions ($X^2=9.15$, $p=0.027$). Moreover, we found a significant effect of median ferritin concentration on frequency of blood transfusion after performing kruskal Wallis test ($H=17.55$, $P= 0.007^*$). After a splenectomy, the interval between blood infusions doubles. In conclusion, the present study reported that a splenectomy reduced the frequency of blood transfusions, Conducting further studies with a considerable sample size in the future will confirm our results.

Keywords: *Thalassemia, splenectomy, ferritin, children, blood transfusion.*

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Introduction

Thalassemia is the most prevalent type of inherited anaemia globally (Weatherall, et al., 2006) According to the World Health Organization reports, 1.5% of the world's population are estimated to be thalassemia carriers and around 60,000 infants are born with a major thalassemia (Modell, & Darlison, 2008). The most prevailing type of chronic hemolytic anaemia in Egypt is beta thalassemia, around 85.1%. Among 1000 normal random inhabitants from various locations in Egypt, the carrier rate was calculated between 9 to 10.2% (El-Beshlawy, et al., 1999). All types of thalassemia are characterized by a defect in the globin synthesis within haemoglobin, resulting in hypochromic microcytic anemia. (Bhagavan, & Chung-Eun, 2011) Thalassemia patients are categorised upon severity into Thalassemia minor: little or no anemia (Hb 9 to 12 g/dL), Thalassemia intermedia: microcytic anemia with Hb often more than 7 g/dL, thus blood transfusions are needed at intervals and Thalassemia major: severe anemia (Hb 1 to 6 g/dL), as a result regular blood transfusions are needed to keep Hb at an accepted level (Rund, & Rachmilewitz, 2005; Falguni Vashi, 2014). Treatment of thalassemia includes blood transfusions, iron chelating agents, folic acid (vit B9) and splenectomy (Falguni Vashi, 2014).

Regular transfusion protocol should only be initiated if the patient suffers from one of the following: hemoglobin level of ≥ 7 g/dl could not be reached or growth impairment or progressive enlargement in spleen size. The aims of regular blood transfusion are: targeting pretransfusion Hb 9-9.5 g/dl by using packaged red blood cells (pRBCs), suppression of erythropoiesis to prevent skeletal deformities, slow progression of splenomegaly and reduction of gastrointestinal iron absorption (Olivieri, 1999).

Splenectomy is needed when blood transfusions surpass 200–250 ml/kg/year of PRBC (Cohen, Gayer, & Mizanin, 1989). Patients on regular PRBC transfusions are vulnerable to the following risks: haemolytic reactions, transmission of infection and iron overload

(Maxwell, & Wilson, 2006). Regular blood transfusions carry the risk of iron toxicity which can be prevented by iron chelation to keep body iron at a safe level or keep tissue iron at a safe level if iron has already been accumulated (Porter, & Shah, 2010).

The aim of the study was the assessment of the prevalence of blood transfusion episodes among thalassemia patients and evaluation of the relationship between the blood transfusion (regarding frequency and type of transfusion) and sociodemographic factors, clinical, and laboratory findings.

Materials and Methods

Study Setting

The study was conducted at Students Sporting Hospital affiliated to the Health Insurance in Alexandria.

Study Design

A cross-sectional study.

Study Population

Target populations: records of the patients aged between 10 months and 18 years who are suffering from thalassemia and undergo blood transfusion as they came at haematology clinic of Students Sporting Hospital affiliated to the Health Insurance in Alexandria.

Inclusion Criteria

Patients were suffering from thalassemia and requiring blood transfusion.

Exclusion Criteria

Patients who received blood transfusions for other causes.

Sample Size

According to previous study of Ragab et al. (2013), the prevalence of blood transfusion among thalassemia patients is expected to be 5 %, level of significance is 5%, and the power is 80% so that the sample size will be 73 participants.

Sample Type

Purposive sample.

Data Collection

The data was collected from the medical records of thalassemia patients (aged between 10 months and 18 years) who undergo blood transfusion from the beginning of January 2024 till the end of June 2024. Data collection comprised 3 parts: personal data, medical sheet and blood investigations. The reference ranges for blood investigations are derived from Dacie and Lewis Practical Hematology guidelines 2017.

Statistical Analysis

The data was exported to SPSS version 26 software. A normality test was performed to assess the data distribution. Since the data did not meet the assumptions of normal distribution, the results were described using the median and interquartile range (IQR). Analytical statistical tests were employed to identify factors influencing the blood transfusion rate in children with thalassemia. These tests included the Chi-square test to analyze relationships between categorical variables and logistic regression analysis to evaluate the predictive effects of independent variables on the transfusion rate.

The researchers have got the ethical committee approval from Ministry of Health and Health Insurance Organization, Egypt.

Results

Table 1 shows a descriptive view on study population of children in Students Sporting hospital, the total number was 73 children 39(53.4%) males and 34(46.6%) females. According to age they were divided into 2 groups: less than or equal to 12 years 16 (21.9%) and over 12 years 57(78.1%). Further categorization was done according to family history as 30(41.1%) of patients were with previous family history with one or more of family members. Blood transfusion frequency ranged from every 10 days 7(9.5%), to every 60 days 1(1.4%), while the majority transferred blood every 15 days 33(45.2%). Classification according to the diagnosis of the children: thalassemia major 64(87.7%) and thalassemia

intermediate 8(11%) and only one child with Sickle thalassemia (1.4%). The complains differ from follow up 69(94.5%), 2 (2.7%) from high ferritin level, 1(1.4%) from jaundice and 1(1.4%) from gastritis.

Table 1. Demographic Characteristics of Study Population (n=73)

Demographic characteristics of the population	and clinical of the study	No	(%)
Patient gender	Male	39	53.4
	Female	34	46.6
Age	≤ 12 years	16	21.9
	>12 years	57	78.1
Family history	Yes	30	41.1
	No	43	58.9
Frequency of blood transfusion	Every 10 day	7	9.5
	Every 15 day	33	45.2
	Every 20 day	4	5.5
	Every 21 day	12	16.4
	Every 30 day	15	20.6
	Every 45 day	1	1.4
	Every 2 months	1	1.4
Diagnosis	Sickle thalassemia	1	1.3
	Thalassemia intermediate	8	11.0
	Thalassemia major	64	87.7
Complain	Follow up	69	94.5
	Follow up and gastritis	1	1.4
	High ferritin level	2	2.7
	Jaundice	1	1.4

Note: significant, $p < 0.05$

The laboratory results for patients categorized into two age groups: ≤12 years and >12 years show key deviations as anemia (RBC, HCT, HGB) in both age groups and elevation in RDW (Red Cell Distribution Width) in both age groups, indicating variation in RBC size. Also thrombocytosis (PLT, PCT) (platelet Count (PLT) and plateletcrit (PCT) Present in younger patients (≤12 years) and elevation of ferritin (iron overload) both groups and low creatinine observed in older patients (>12 years). as shown in table 2.

Table 2. Laboratory Results of Study Ppulation (n=73)

Age group	≤12 tears (N=9)		More than 12 years (N= 64)	
Lab results	Median	IQR*	Median	IQR
WBCS	8.05	5.8-15.2	6.4	5.5-7.3
RBCS	3.2	2.6-3.4	2.98	2.2-6.1
HCT	23.7	20.3-25.1	20.8	13.7-25.0
HGB	8	7.0-8.5	7.1	6.1-7.9
MCH	25.4	23.5-27.6	24.5	23.3-26.2
MCV	75.7	65.9-79.3	74.2	66.2-77.5
MCHC	34.6	32.4-36.0	31.6	27.5-34.6
RDW	21.3	16.3-30.5	27.4	17.4-43.1
PLT	401.5	237.5-785.0	322.0	198.0-398.0
MPV	9.5	7.9-12.0	9.3	8.7-10.6
PCT	0.46	0.25-0.91	0.3	0.17-0.91
PDW	18.7	15.3-27.6	17.9	15.9-36.25
Ferritin	1282.9	729.7-2204.4	1637.0	914.0-2146.4
Creatinine	0.5	0.37-0.7	0.37	0.34-0.5
Urea	24.0	20.0-28.0	24.0	17.5-30.5
ALT	20.0	11.0-34.7	18.0	14.5-33.0
AST	24.0	19.2-38.0	30.0	21.5-36.5

Note: IQR: interquartile range, WBC (White Blood Cells), RBC (Red Blood Cells), HCT (Hematocrit), HGB (Hemoglobin), MCH (Mean Corpuscular Hemoglobin), MCV (Mean Corpuscular Volume), MCHC (Mean Corpuscular Hemoglobin Concentration), RDW (Red Cell Distribution Width), PLT (Platelets), MPV (Mean Platelet Volume), PCT (Plateletcrit), PDW (Platelet Distribution Width), ALT (Alanine Aminotransferase), AST (Aspartate Aminotransferase) (Platelet Distribution Width), ALT (Alanine Aminotransferase), AST (Aspartate Aminotransferase)

Table 3 indicates the factors affecting the frequency of blood transfusion in children suffering from thalassemia, dividing the frequency into 4 groups (every 10 days, every 15 days, every 20 or 21 days, and every 30 days or more) and performing multinomial logistic regression analysis, it was found that splenectomy significantly affect the frequency of

blood transfusion ($X^2=9.15$, $p=0.027$) and diagnosis (classified into thalassemia major, intermediate and sickle thalassemia) has a significant effect on frequency of blood transfusion ($X^2=14.85$, $p=0.021$). age, sex, address and patient complain have no significant effect on frequency of blood transfusion.

Table 3. Factors Affecting the Frequency of Blood Transfusion in Thalassemia Patients (n=73)

Predictors	-2 Log Likelihood	Chi-Square	df	p-value
Intercept	44.34	0.000	0	.
Address	49.45	5.11	3	0.164
Complain	57.80	13.46	12	0.336
Splenectomy	53.49	9.15	3	0.027*
Age	45.79	1.45	3	0.693
Sex	47.09	2.75	3	0.431
Diagnosis	59.19	14.85	6	0.021*

Note: significant, $p<0.05$

The findings indicated that there was no significant effect of prescribing one chelating agent (53 (72.6%), two chelating agents (4(5.5%)

or even no chelating agents (16(21.9%) and frequency of blood transfusion ($X^2=9.71$, $p=0.56$)

Also hydroxyl urea indicated in 38 (52.0%) of cases and has no significant effect on frequency of blood transfusion ($\chi^2=3.4$, $p=0.64$). folic acid prescribed in 64 (87.6%) of cases with no significant effect on frequency of blood transfusion ($\chi^2=4.6$, $p=0.46$).

The Kruskal Wallis test revealed a significant effect of blood transfusion on median ferritin concentration ($H=17.55$, $P= 0.007^*$).

The association between frequency of blood transfusion and sociodemographic and clinical characteristics of study population was tested by using chi square test, it was found that there is a significant association between frequency of blood transfusion and diagnosis (Thalassemia major=64 (87.4%), Thalassemia intermediate=8 (11%) and sickle Thalassemia=1(1.3%)) ($\chi^2=27.9$, $p=0.006$) and address in Alexandria (urban areas=67(91.8%), rural areas=6(8.2%)) ($\chi^2=27.2$, $p= <0.001$). There was no significant association between frequency of blood transfusion and age group, sex, family history and splenectomy.

Discussion

In line with a Pakistani study conducted in the Department of Pediatric Surgery in collaboration with the haematology, radiology, anaesthesia, and paediatric intensive care department at The Children's Hospital and the Institute of Child Health, Multan, between September 2007 and September 2013, our study found that the percentage of male patients was 53.4 percent, higher than the percentage of female patients, which registered 46.6 percent. This finding supported the hypothesis that the disease is more common in males (Akhtar, et al., 2016)

Cappellini MD et al. (2021) found that 86% of participants had blood transfusions every 2-5 weeks. This is consistent with another study done in Cyprus, which found that patients with TD β -thalassemia require lifetime care with frequent RBC transfusions every 2-5 weeks. This result shows that thalassemia patients are at risk for developing iron overload and accompanying endocrine problems, erythrocyte alloimmunization, transfusion reactions, and infections.

The current study found that splenectomy had a significant effect on the frequency of blood transfusions ($\chi^2=9.15$, $p=0.027$). The objective for splenectomy in patients with TDT is to reduce blood consumption and transfusion requirements, with the ultimate goal of lowering iron excess (Rachmilewitz, & Giardina, 2011).

After a splenectomy, the time between blood transfusions doubles. The need for blood transfusions decreased from 250 ml/kg/year to 125 ml/kg/year in the Thailand research, and the first time between transfusions grew from two weeks to more than a month. Stated differently, the annual number of blood transfusions dropped from 24 to 12. This finding can be interpreted as that treatment choices can lower the number of times people visit medical facilities, which benefits patients' financial well-being (Hathirat, et al., 1989).

In our study, we found a significant effect of median ferritin concentration on frequency of blood transfusion after performing Kruskal Wallis test ($H=17.55$, $P= 0.007^*$). This finding coincides with Indian study which indicated that there was a statistically significant correlation between increased serum ferritin levels with increasing number of a total blood transfusion (Bhalodiya, et al. 2023).

Limitations of the Study

The research had some limitations, as the study was conducted at governmental hospital which introduced free health care services for patients, so the results cannot be generalized for private sectors. Additionally, the unavailability of electronic medical records which could affect the accuracy of the data.

Despite these limitations, the study provides valuable local data on thalassemia children. This information can be used by researchers and authorities to improve the medical service of thalassemia patients.

Conclusion

The current study investigated the medical records of 73 thalassemia patients aged between 10 months and 18 years, all of them were found to undergo blood transfusion at different intervals at Students Sporting Hospital affiliated

to the Health Insurance in Alexandria, most of them are thalassemia major patients. The highest blood transfusion frequency among the patients was noted (every 15 days). The following factors had no significance on frequency of blood transfusions: hydroxurea intake, folic acid intake and demographic characteristics of sampled patients (age, sex, address and patient complain). However, splenectomy reduced the frequency of blood transfusions. Conducting further studies with a considerable sample size in the future will confirm our results

Conflict of Interests

The authors of the current study would like to declare that there is no conflict of interest.

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